

Influence of Celebrity Endorsement on Consumer Brand Preference of Infinix Mobile Phones among Undergraduates of Select Tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Despite the huge financial commitment by advertisers to celebrity endorsement, it has been observed that it is difficult to get 100% returns on investment on products and services celebrity endorsements are used for. Hence the study investigated the influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer's brand preference for Infinix Mobile phones with the following objectives; to Investigate whether celebrity endorsement influences consumers' brand preference for Infinix Mobile Phones and; to find out whether Information about celebrity endorsers affects the purchasing decision of Infinix Mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Companies may withdraw their endorsement from celebrities due to various scandals and this scandals can cause people not to patronise the product due to the celebrity involved. Nigeria. Using the Yamane formula, the sample size was 387 respondents randomly selected from Adeleke University, Redeemers' University, and Osun State University, Osogbo campus undergraduates. Questionnaire served as the instrument for data collection. Hypothesis one and two were tested using analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) respectively. Findings revealed that celebrity endorsement have an influence on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones and that information about celebrity endorsers also affects the purchasing decision of Infinix Mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. Nigerian celebrities have the persuasive ability to influence brand recall as well as brand association which significantly influences brand preference most especially among undergraduates. Therefore, care must be taken to scrutinise a celebrity's lifestyle and the person's present social acceptance before endorsement to avoid any negative image that could have a negative effect on brands, while sustaining the use of celebrity endorsements as an advertising strategy. This study adds to existing research in celebrity endorsement on consumer brand preference with reference to Infinix Mobile phone and it current celebrity endorser (Davido) has not been study.

Keywords: Celebrity endorsement, Consumer, Brand preference, Infinix mobile phones, Undergraduates

Introduction

Advertising is an important practice use to inform the consumers about a product and generates demand for a product or service (Hasan, 2013). As indicated by Bellman et al. (2010), advertisement avoidance, fast-forwarded advertisements, and 'eyes off-screen' exposure were found to be inferior to full attention exposures. 'Eyes off-screen' occurs when the viewer can in any case hear the advertisement, despite not watching it, or paying any particular attention to the advertisement at all; through this subliminal listening, the viewer will unintentionally pick up something from the advertisement (cited in Sahid & Aluko, 2022). Advertising does not do what it was meant to do when it is avoided by the viewers which have put a strain on advertisers.

Advertisers, as well as advertising agencies, have devised various advertising strategies to improve patronage of their products and services, since consumers cannot be forced to watch or listen to continuous radio or television advertisements or to spend more time on newspaper and magazine. Hence, this has prompted the utilisation of celebrity endorsement for further improvement on awareness, as well as improving sales.

In Nigeria, as in many other nations of the world, the concept of celebrity endorsement has evolved. Corporations and governments are increasingly relying on the popularity of specific celebrities to convey a message or promote a brand. It was assumed that integrating a celebrity into a brand would increase the chances of product sales, which made companies value the

business ideal of a celebrity endorser (Egbeh et al., 2020). For instance, the appearance of a celebrity in a television commercial may draw viewers' attention to an advert. Celebrities are well-liked and followed by a large number of people, so, understandably, advertisers will profit from using them to spread their message (Randhawa & Khan, 2014). Hence, it is observed that celebrity may draw attention to a brand, connect it to their profile, and compare their positive qualities with those of the product in question.

The celebrity endorsement marketing tactic has become much more prevalent with the rapid growth of micro-blogging platforms (social media), such as Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook, among others. Brands are now using social media platforms to gain visibility in the college-age audience (Burke, 2017), while leveraging on celebrities as a social media influencer which represent a relatively new version of marketing tactic in the social media age called influencer marketing. Conceptually, celebrities are different from influencer in nature (Dhanesh & Duthler, 2019), While celebrities are famous for their activities outside of social media (e.g. sports, music, and acting), on the other hand, influencers are known for their activities on social media, most especially creating relatable content that appeals with their audience (Tafesse & Wood, 2021). Therefore, influencers' reputation derives solely from the content they post and their social media activity (Schouten et al., 2019). They often focus on a more specific audience with whom they have similar interests, as a sort of an online friend. Because influencers are perceived to be connected to their target audience, they also tend to appear more trustworthy (Lou & Yuan, 2019) or credible (Sokolova & Kefi, 2020) than conventional celebrities.

Belch and Belch (2012) mentioned that consumers are more easily influenced by a message that comes from a person with whom they can relate or feel close. However, there are cases whereby celebrity endorsement goes wrong, when the celebrity's credibility as in case of scandal is under intense scrutiny and also, when the celebrity is perceived as someone who is not fit to endorse a particular brand. An instance is a male celebrity endorsing a sanitary pad; this may send a wrong signal to the consumer. Furthermore, celebrity endorsing multiple brands may give the impression that the celebrity will endorse anything for financial benefit.

With the advancement of technology and development of sophisticated smartphones, competition in the smartphone business forces company like Infinix mobile phone to continue to improve their marketing strategy, every smartphone company are trying to be more excited about doing marketing activities by making use of Celebrity Endorsement in promotional activities (Zipporah & Mberia, 2014).

With the increasing use of celebrity endorsement in the smartphone industry in Nigeria and the dominance of smartphone usage among the majority of undergraduates, young people are presented with varieties of smartphones to choose from which has led to the prevalence of mobile phone preference among undergraduates with the students having various reasons for choosing a particular brand of phone over the other or choosing a new brand over previously used phone known as brand switch. Celebrity endorsement tends to persuade consumers to fix their choices from numerous and competing brands. As Adebayo (2020), rightly said, celebrity endorsement is an advertising tool that seeks to leverage the fame quotient, acceptability, reliability, and audience base of a celebrity to positively influence brand perception, boost interest and drive sales.

In a study by Nnamocha and Chukundah (2018) carried out on the relationship between celebrity endorsements and customer patronage, using the Nigeria Bottling Company (NBC) Port Harcourt as the unit of study. The study held that there is a significant relationship between endorsement coverage and repeat purchase of beverages, as well as a significant relationship between frequency of endorsements and customer brand loyalty to beverages.

Ike (2015) worked on Influence of Celebrity Endorsement on Consumer Brand Preference of Selected Beverage Brands in Nigeria. The result revealed that celebrity endorsement had a

significant influence on consumers' preference for firms' brands and celebrity endorsement significantly facilitated brand switch by consumers of beverages.

Okoye et al. (2017) examined the influence of the use of celebrities in MTN Nigeria advertisements on University of Nigeria Nsukka undergraduate students. Findings of the research among others revealed that celebrity-endorsed advert has a significant influence on customers' purchase intention. While little had been done on Infinix mobile phone and celebrity endorsement, this study investigated the influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phone among undergraduates of select tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

Celebrity endorsement is a form of advertising campaign which uses celebrity fame to promote a product, brand, or service or to raise awareness about an issue. However, where celebrity's credibility goes under intense scrutiny is when the celebrity is perceived as someone who's personality maybe is not fit to endorse such product an instance is the political party, All Progressive Congress (APC) using musical artist, Habeeb Okikiola known as Portable during the Osun State Election which created reactions across social media (Royal, 2022). Also, celebrity scandals are believed to affect the brand image and sales which leads to revoking of celebrity endorsement deals. For instance, in the year 2021, Nigerian music sensation Tiwa Savage lost her endorsement deals with Cadbury, Pampers, and Glo among others, over her leaked sex tape (Adebayo, 2021).

Furthermore, some scholars have argued that celebrity endorsement could affect brand preference if the celebrity endorser has a negative reputation, are included in scandals or other types of bad publicity (White et al., 2009). In most cases, companies do not wait to verify the outcome of such a scandal before terminating the endorsement deal. When a celebrity comes negatively into the news, companies believe that such negative news will affect the brand image and sales, which leads to the revoking of the endorsement deal of the Celebrity (Tylee, 2010).

Nigerian celebrities have the persuasive ability to influence brand recall as well as brand association, but their persuasive ability sometimes do not influence brand preference (Adetunji & Adetunji, 2019) as the brand quality, price, and design of a product have a great influence on consumer brand preference of mobile phone brands among students (Adetunji & Adetunji, 2019). Further argument revealed that for effective advertisement, the endorser necessarily does not need to be a celebrity (Schouten et al., 2019) in order to influence consumer preference. This study tends to improve on existing literature and relevancy of the influence of celebrity endorsement, while focusing on Infinix mobile phone. Hence, the present study.

Research questions

- i. What is the influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the extent of the influence of information about celebrity endorser on purchasing decisions of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance

- H₁. Celebrity endorsement has significant influence on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

- H₂. There is significant relationship between information about celebrity endorser and purchasing decisions of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

Literature review and theoretical framework

A celebrity is an individual who is well-known among a large group of people with attributes as attractiveness and an extraordinary lifestyle, it can be said that celebrities generally differ from the social norm and enjoy a high level of public awareness within a corresponding social group (Schlecht, 2003) which advertisers are relying on the popularity of a celebrity to promote their brands.

Celebrity endorsement is an advertising strategy in which companies use well-known people as spokespersons for their products. Celebrity endorsement as defined by Okafor (2011) is a strategy of persuasion where customers relate or identify with the person used or featured in an advert (cited in Okorie & Agbaleke, 2017). Hence, celebrity endorsement is a key concept that has evolved into a common advertising strategy to link and transfer the qualities of the celebrity that are aspired to and liked by the consumer, such as physique, health or lifestyle to the brand (Leslie, 2011). This is done to create a mental association between the brand and the celebrity in the mind of the consumer. Furthermore, the approach is necessary to increase the attractiveness of the product and the likelihood of influencing consumer preferences and purchase intentions regarding that particular product (Leslie 2011). Celebrity endorsements are effective not just in establishing credibility and trust for the brands they promote (Johansson & Bozan, 2017), but also in attracting the target audience (Okorie & Agbaleke, 2017). For celebrity endorsement to establish any form of credibility, consumers will have to perceive the celebrity endorser as possessing attractiveness, trustworthiness, likeness, familiarity and expertise relevant to the communication topic and can be trusted to give an objective opinion on a particular subject matter (Aziz et al., 2013; Ermeç et al., 2014).

With the rapid adoption of smart-phones usage across the world and Nigeria in particular, smart phone users are faced with the difficult task of choosing which brand to purchase or use. Current literature shows that consumer preference is influenced by a variety of factors such as features of the product, product quality, social factors, brand name, income, price, personal factors, and celebrity endorsement among others.

Riyath and Musthafa (2014) carried out a study on factors affecting the choice of a particular mobile phone brand among students at Sri Lankan University. The research findings showed that product features were highly considered by students as an important factor when selecting their preferred brands. Similarly, a study conducted by Negi and Pandey (2013) on factors influencing brand preference for mobile phones. The study results showed that product features had a significant influence on consumers' decisions over which brand to buy. Furthermore, Adetunji and Adetunji (2019) investigated mobile buying behaviour in Nigeria. The price was discovered to be most influential among students' communities among several factors, like the shape and brand of mobile phones with an exception of celebrity endorsement. While most of the study above did not pay much attention to celebrity endorsement as a factor for consumer brand preference in their research, but other studies gave credence to the influence of celebrity endorsement. For Omoregbe and Osifo (2019) research on the impact of celebrity endorsement on the consumer purchasing behaviour of four brands of telecommunication network operators in Nigerian among students of the University of Benin, Benin City, the findings revealed that all celebrity endorsement attributes have a positive and significant link with the purchase decisions of the consumers. In addition, Okoye et al (2017) study on the influence of the use of celebrities in MTN Nigeria advertisements on University of Nigeria Nsukka undergraduate students shows that celebrity-endorsed advert has a significant influence on customers' purchase intention.

Ahmed et al., (2014) suggested that the use of celebrity endorsement in communicating the message about the features of a brand is most effective.

The Source Credibility Theory as propounded by Carl Hovland and Walter Weiss in 1951 explores the characteristic of communicators' impacts on the receiver's perception and the level of message acceptance (Anaeto et al., 2008). In other words, the theory posited on the assumption that people are more likely to accept and influenced by a message once the source presents itself as credible. The theory contends that the effectiveness of a message depends upon the perceived level of attractiveness, expertise and trustworthiness associated with an endorser or communicator (Belch & Belch, 2012). Based on this theory, it is expected that for celebrity endorsement strategy to be effective, the source which is the celebrity in this case has to be perceived as credible by the consumers, that is, the source has to be an expert, trustworthy and attractive. The more credibility a celebrity endorser enjoys, the better the image of the brand that he/she endorses. In other words, a celebrity can transfer his or her credibility to the product he or she endorses.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey design of 387 undergraduates in select tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria, using Yamane (1967) formula to determine the sample size. The study employed a multistage sampling technique, A simple random technique was used to select two private universities (Adeleke University, Ede, Osun state, Redeemers University, Ede, Osun State) among eight private university and one public university (Osun State University, Osogbo Campus, Osun State) among 2 public universities in Osun State, while a proportionate sample size was gotten using: $k = \frac{n}{N} \times A$ with Adeleke University having 101 sample to select, Redeemers' University having 112 sample to select while Osun State University, Osogbo campus having 174 sample to select. Thereafter respondent were randomly selected. Out of 387 copies of the questionnaire administered, 331 (85.5%) were returned useful. A content validity was adopted for the instrument with an internal consistency of 0.818 reliability. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 21.0 was the statistical software utilised to analyse the research questions. One-way ANOVA was used to analyse hypothesis 1, while Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was utilised in analysing hypotheses 2.

Data presentation and analysis

Demographic information of the respondents

Study analysis revealed that 54.1% (179) of the respondents were females (AU=53.8%; RUN = 45.4% and UNIOSUN = 46.1%) while 45.9% (152) were males (AU= 46.2%; RUN = 45.4% and UNIOSUN = 45.9%). Also, 38.1% (126) of the respondents were within the age of 15 – 18 years (AU=37.6%; RUN = 38.1% and UNIOSUN = 38.3%), 33.8% (112) were within 19 - 22 years (AU=33.3%; RUN = 34.0% and UNIOSUN = 34.1%), 18.7% (62) were within 23 – 26 years (AU=19.3%; RUN = 18.6% and UNIOSUN = 18.4%) while 9.4% (31) were within 27 – 30 years (AU=9.8%; RUN = 9.3% and UNIOSUN = 9.2%).

Reserch question one: What is the influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary Institution in Osun State

ITEMS	SA		A		D		SD		N		Mean	STD
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Celebrity endorsement is an important factor when choosing a preferred brand	122	36.9	131	39.6	20	6.0	21	6.3	37	11.2	4.63	0.987
Celebrity endorsement makes me not to care about the quality, price and design of Infinix mobile	89	26.9	129	39.0	52	15.7	25	7.6	36	10.9	3.55	0.901

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Celebrity endorsement necessitates a repeat purchase of infinix mobile phone.	103	31.1	111	33.5	51	15.4	21	6.3	45	13.6	4.16	0.956	
The usage of Infinix mobile phone by the celebrity endorser (Davido) Influence my preference for the brand	123	37.2	133	40.2	22	6.6	21	6.3	32	9.7	4.65	0.966	
I will choose a brand with a celebrity endorser over a brand without a celebrity endorser	132	39.9	129	39.0	27	8.2	23	6.9	20	6.0	4.71	0.880	
The use of a celebrity endorser gives credibility to the quality of infinix mobile	118	35.6	141	42.6	22	6.6	19	5.7	31	9.4	4.45	0.876	
My brand preference of Infinix mobile phone is determined by the price, quality and design	87	26.3	119	36.0	51	15.4	31	9.4	43	13.0	3.63	0.938	
Certification by the celebrity endorser that infinix mobile has a good quality nessesitate my preference for the brand.	117	35.3	134	40.5	21	6.3	17	5.1	44	13.3	4.43	0.876	
My preference of Infinix Mobile phone is based on recommendation from family and friends	77	23.3	93	28.1	57	17.2	52	15.7	52	15.7	3.23	0.904	
Celebrity endorsement determines my preference for Infinix mobile phone	119	36.0	121	36.6	37	11.2	23	6.9	31	9.4	4.55	0.953	

Weighted mean = 4.20; Arithmetic mean = 42.01, STD = 9.237

Source: The Researcher Field Survey 2022

Key: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)

Decision rule: if mean is 1.00 - 1.79 = low influence, 1.80 – 2.50 = low influence, 2.50 – 3.00 moderate, 3.00 – 3.99; high influence, 4.00 – 5.00 very high influence, Criterion mean = 3.0

Table 1 revealed that the majority of the respondents affirmed that celebrity endorsement influences consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria with a weighted mean score of 4.20 on a scale Of 5. Specifically, most of the respondents agreed to the varying extent that they would choose a brand with a celebrity endorser over a brand without a celebrity endorser (mean = 4.71), celebrity endorsement is an important factor when choosing a preferred brand (mean = 4.63), Celebrity endorsement determines my preference for Infinix mobile phone (mean = 4.55), the use of a celebrity endorser gives credibility to the quality of infinix mobile (mean = 4.45) and that certification by the celebrity endorser that infinix mobile has a good quality necessitate my preference for the brand (mean = 4.43).

Research question two: What is the extent of the influence of information about celebrity endorser on purchasing decisions of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Influence of information about Celebrity endorser on the purchasing decision of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary institutions

ITEMS	SA		A		D		SD		N		Mean	STD
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Infinix mobile phone celebrity endorsement creates a positive brand image in the mind of the consumers	125	37.8	138	41.7	20	6.0	21	6.3	27	8.2	4.53	0.801
Information about the celebrity endorser influences my purchasing decision	115	34.7	130	39.3	32	9.7	21	6.3	33	10.0	4.44	0.891
Goodwill of the celebrity endorser affects the purchasing decision of the consumer.	101	30.5	126	38.1	41	12.4	22	6.6	41	12.4	3.79	0.846

Scandalous Information about the celebrity endorser (Davido) may stop me from purchasing Infinix mobile phone	113	34.1	133	40.2	22	6.6	21	6.3	42	12.7	4.38	0.865
Controversial information surrounding the celebrity endorser discourages me from purchasing Infinix mobile phone.	104	31.4	119	36.0	30	9.1	25	7.6	53	16.0	3.65	0.982
Weighted mean = 4.16; Arithmetic mean = 20.79; STD = 4.385												

Source: The Researcher Field Survey 2022

Table 2 revealed that the majority of the respondents affirmed that information about celebrity endorser affects the purchasing decision of Infinix Mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria with a weighted mean score of 4.16. Specifically, the majority of the respondents agreed that Infinix mobile phone celebrity endorsement creates a positive brand image in the mind of the consumers (mean = 4.53), information about the celebrity endorser influences my purchasing decision (mean = 4.44) and the Goodwill of the celebrity endorser affects the purchasing decision of the consumer (mean = 3.79). On the other hand, a significant number of respondents claimed that negative information about the celebrity endorser affects their purchasing decision of infinix phone as apparent in the responses: Scandalous Information about the celebrity endorser (Davido) may stop me from purchasing Infinix mobile phone (mean = 4.38) and Controversial information surrounding the celebrity endorser discourages me from purchasing Infinix mobile phone (mean = 3.65).

Decision rule

In this study, if the significance of the tests exceeds the pre-set level of significance (0.05), then the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis rejected, but if the p-value is lesser than 0.05, the null hypothesis will be rejected and the alternative will be accepted.

Hypothesis one: Celebrity endorsement has a significant influence on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria

Table 3: Influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates

Source of Variation	Sum of Square	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between groups	12.957	3	4.319	8.010	0.000*
Within groups	176.324	327	.539		
Total	189.281	175			

Source: The Researcher Field Survey 2022

The result of hypothesis one is presented in Table 3. The independent variable (celebrity endorsement) and the dependent variable (consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among Undergraduates of selected tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria) was analysed using One Way ANOVA. Table 1 revealed that the significance of the composite contribution of the prediction was tested at $\alpha < 0.05$ using the F- ratio at the degrees of freedom (df = 3, 327). Also, it could be observed from the Table that the analysis of variance for the regression yielded an F-ratio of 8.010 (significant at a 0.05 level). The null hypothesis (H_{01}) is therefore rejected.

Hypothesis two: There is significant relationship between Information about celebrity endorser and purchasing decisions of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Relationship between information about celebrity endorser and purchasing decision of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria

Variables	Mean	St. dev.	N	Df	R	Sig. p.	Remark
Information about celebrity endorser purchasing decision of	20.79	4.385	331	2	0.627	0.000	Sig.

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Source: The Researcher Field Survey 2022

The result of the hypothesis shown in Table 4 using the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) revealed that there was a positive and significant relationship between information about celebrity endorser and Purchasing decision of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria ($r=0.627$; $P < 0.05$). The result showed a strong positive correlation between information about celebrity endorser and purchasing decisions of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria at a strong level. The correlation is statistically significant at a 0.05 significance level. This means that there is a strong, positive, and significant relationship between information about celebrity endorser and Purchasing decisions of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria as indicated in Table 4 ($r = 0.627$, $N = 331$, $p < 0.05$). Based on the results, null hypothesis (H_{02}) is rejected.

Discussion of the findings

RQ1: What is the influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?

Finding revealed that most of the undergraduates in the study confirmed that celebrity endorsement influences consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria as they agreed that they would choose a brand with a celebrity endorser over a brand without a celebrity endorser; celebrity endorsement is an important factor when choosing a preferred brand; Celebrity endorsement determines their preference for Infinix mobile phone and that the use of a celebrity endorser gives credibility to the quality of infinix mobile. In other words, the influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates cannot be overemphasised. This finding corroborates Ike (2015) that that celebrity endorsement had a significant influence on consumers' preference of firms' brands and celebrity endorsement significantly facilitated brand switch by consumers of beverages.

RQ2: What is the extent of the influence of information about celebrity endorser on purchasing decisions of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?

Findings revealed that the majority of the respondents affirmed that information about celebrity endorser affects the purchasing decision of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. This result implies that most of the undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Osun State agreed that information about celebrity endorser affects the purchasing decision of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria as positive information about the celebrity endorser affects purchasing decision positively while negative information about the celebrity endorser affects the purchasing decision negatively. Specifically, scandalous and controversial information about the celebrity endorser discourages the respondents from purchasing Infinix mobile phones while goodwill and positive information about the celebrity endorser affect the purchasing decision of the consumers. Additionally, it was found that Infinix mobile phone celebrity endorsement creates a positive brand image in the mind of the consumers. The finding lends credence to the study of Johansson and Bozan (2017) that the image of the celebrity endorser transfers to the brand image. Furthermore, trustworthiness was shown as important factors in a celebrity endorser. Also, the research shows that attributes such as familiarity, likability, and similarity in a celebrity endorser affect consumers' purchase intention. Furthermore, the findings affirmed the source credibility theory that the source

which is the celebrity in this case has to be perceived as credible by the consumers. The more credibility a celebrity endorser enjoys, the better the image of the brand that he/she endorses.

H₁. Celebrity endorsement has a significant influence on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

Finding of hypothesis one on the influence of the celebrity endorsement on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates revealed that celebrity endorsement had a significant positive influence on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. This result suggests that celebrity endorsement had a favourable influence on consumer brand preference of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. Hence, for consumer brand preference of infinix mobile phones among the undergraduates in tertiary institutions to be enhanced, the use of celebrity endorsements as an advertising strategy needs to be sustained.

H₂. There is a significant relationship between information about celebrity endorser and purchasing decisions of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of selected tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

Finding of the hypothesis two revealed that information about celebrity endorser had a significant relationship with purchasing decisions of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. This implies that the undergraduates in tertiary institutions in Osun State rely on the information about celebrity endorser to form their purchasing decisions of infinix mobile phones. In other words, as information about celebrity endorser improves, there is a tendency that there would be a corresponding improvement in purchasing decisions of Infinix mobile phones among undergraduates of select tertiary Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

Conclusion and recommendations

The study examined the extent to which celebrity endorsement influences consumer brand preference of infinix mobile among undergraduates of select tertiary institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. Nigerian celebrities have the persuasive ability to influence brand recall as well as brand association which significantly influences brand choice or preference most especially among undergraduates. Therefore, care must be taken to scrutinise a celebrity's lifestyle and the person's present social acceptance before signing an endorsement with such a celebrity to avoid any negative image that could have a negative effect on Infinix mobile phones. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made.

- i. For a celebrity to be used on a product as a brand endorser, the marketing strategy has to be deployed such that the celebrity to be used must have an acceptable social standing to have purchasing influence on consumer patronage of the product among the undergraduates in Nigerian universities.
- ii. There is the need to take precautions when using celebrities to endorse products in order not to get a negative outcome; and organisational managers should not overlook other important strategies, even as they work to get the best out of celebrity endorsement.
- iii. For consumer brand preference of infinix mobile phones among the undergraduates in tertiary institutions to be enhanced, the use of celebrity endorsements as an advertising strategy needs to be sustained.
- iv. Manufacturers should use more celebrity endorsements to build consciousness and perceptions of their products in the minds of consumers. This could be achieved by devising a suitable strategy to identify the right celebrity endorsement attributes that would lead to improved competitiveness as the combined effect is greater than the use of one attribute.

References

- Adebayo, S., (2021). Sex Tape: Tiwa Savage Reportedly Loses Endorsement Deals. Retrieve from <https://tribuneonlineng.com/sex-tape-tiwa-savage-reportedly-loses-endorsement-deals/>
- Adebayo, Y. (2020). Corporate Nigeria and celebrity endorsement: How much influence can entertainers truly wield? Retrieved from www.newtelegraphng.com.
- Adetunji, A.T., & Adetunji, A.V. (2019). Price and consumer's buying behaviour toward android phones in Delta State. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*. 11, 3321–3329.
- Ahmed, N., Farooq, O., & Iqbal, J. (2014). Credibility of Celebrity Endorsement and Buying Intentions an Evidence from Students of Islamabad, Pakistan. *International Letters of Social and Humanistic Sciences*. pp 1-13 doi:10.18052/www.scipress.com/ILSHS.20.1
- Anaeto, S. G, Onabanjo, O. S & Osifeso, T. B. (2008). *Models and Theories of Communication*. Bowie, Maryland: African Renaissance Books.
- Aziz, S., Ghani, U., Niazi, A. (2013). Impact of celebrity credibility on advertising effectiveness. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences*. pp. 107-127 <http://hdl.handle.net/10419/188078>
- Belch, M., & Belch G., (2012). *Advertising and Promotion: Advertising and Promotion: An Integrated Marketing Communications Perspective (5th ed)*. New York: McGraw Hill Irwin.
- Bellman, S., Schweda, A. & Varan, D. (2010) The Residual Impact of Avoided Television Advertising. *Journal of Advertising*.
- Burke, K. (2017). *Social Butterflies: How Social Media Influencers are the New Celebrity Endorsement*. [Dissertation, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University]. vtechworks.lib.vt.edu
- Dhanesh, G. & Duthler, G. (2019). Relationship management through social media influencers: Effects of followers' awareness of paid endorsement. *Public Relations Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2019.03.002>
- Egbeh, P., Nkwocha, C., & Oguguo, F. (2020). The Use Of Celebrity Endorsement In Product Promotions: A Qualitative Appraisal. *International Journal of Business & Law Research*. <https://seahipaj.org/journals-ci/dec-2020/IJBLR/full/IJBLR-D-11-2020.pdf>
- Ermeç, A., Catli, O., Korkmaz, S. (2014). Examining the Effect of Endorser Credibility on the Consumers' Buying Intentions: An Empirical Study in Turkey. *International Review of Management and Marketing*. pp.66-77. Retrieve from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/316841917_Examining_the_Effect_of_Endorser_Credibility_on_the_Consumers'_Buying_Intentions_An_Empirical_Study_in_Turkey
- Hasan, S. (2013). *Mass Communication: Principles and Concepts*. (2nd Ed) New Delhi: CBS Publisher
- Ike, B., (2015). *Influence of Celebrity Endorsement on Consumer Brand Preference of Selected Beverage Brands in Nigeria*. [Masters' Dissertation, University Of Nigeria, Enugu]
- Johansson, M. & Bozan, Ö. (2017), How does celebrity endorsement affect consumers' perception on brand image and purchase intention?. Research Project, Luleå University of Technology, Sweden.
- Leslie, L. Z. (2011). *Celebrity in the 21st Century*. California: ABC.
- Lou, C. & Yuan, S. (2019). Influencer marketing: how message value and credibility affect consumer trust of branded content on Social Media. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15252019.2018.1533501>
- Negi, N., & Pandey, K. (2013). Factors Influencing Brand preference for Mobile Phones: With Reference To Dehradun Youth. *International Journal of Management Research & Business Strategy*. DOI:10.13140/RG.2.1.4248.8083

- Nnamoncha, O. & Chikundah, T. (2018). Celebrity Endorsement and Customer Patronage: A study of Nigeria Bottling Company, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. *Journal of Economic and Management Science*. 1(3), p45. <http://doi.org/10.30560/jems.v1n3p45>
- Okorie, N., & Agbaleke, D. (2017). Celebrity Endorsement Influence on Brand Credibility: A Critical Review of Previous Studies. *Online Journal of Communication and Media Technologies*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.29333/ojcm/2577>
- Okoye, G. , Nwogbo, V. , Ugwuanyi, F. & Okafor, T. (2017). Consumers' perception of the use of Celebrities in Advertising by MTN Nigeria: A study of University of Nigeria Nsukka Undergraduate Students. *International Journal of Research Culture Society*. <http://ijrcs.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/201707003.pdf>
- Omoregbe, O & Osifo, S.J. (2019). Celebrity Endorsement and Consumer Purchasing Behaviour among Students of the University of Benin: A Case Study of the Nigerian Telecommunication Industry. *Amity Journal of Marketing*,4(1),18-32.
- Randhawa, A., & Khan, J. A. (2014). Impact of Celebrity Endorsement on Consumer Buying Behaviour. *International Journal of Business Management*, 1(2), 170-189.
- Riyath, M. I. M., & Musthafa, S. L. (2014). Factors Affecting Mobile Phone Brand Preference Empirical Study on Sri Lanka. Paper presented at the Fourth International Symposium, South Eastern University of Sri Lanka. Munich: GRIN Verlag, pp.378- 388. Retrieve from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/310597210_Factors_Affecting_Mobile_Phone_Brand_Preference_Empirical_Study_on_Sri_Lankan_University_Students
- Royal, D. (2022). Fans mock ‘upcoming’ singer, Portable, as Davido’s uncle wins Osun election. Retrieve from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2022/07/fans-mock-upcoming-singer-portable-as-davidos-uncle-wins-osun-election/>
- Sahid, A. & Aluko, O. (2022). Audience Perception of Product Placement in Nollywood Movies: A Study of The Wedding Party 2. *IMSU Journal of Communication Studies*. Retrieve from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/363729419_Audience_Perception_of_Product_Placement_in_Nollywood_Movies_A_Study_of_The_Wedding_Party_2
- Schouten, A., Janssen, L., & Verspaget, M. (2019). Celebrity vs Influencer endorsement in advertising: the role of identification, credibility, and product-endorser fit. *International Journal of Advertising*. doi:10.1080/02650487.2019.1634898
- Sokolova, K.& Kefi, H. (2020). Instagram and Youtube bloggers promote it, why should I buy? How credibility and parasocial interaction influence purchase intentions. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retconser.2019.01.011>
- Tafesse, W. & Wood, B. (2021). Followers’ engagement with instagram influencers’ content and engagement strategy. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2020.102303>
- Tylee, J. (2010). When Brand Ambassadors go bad. Retrieve from <http://www.campaignlive.co.uk/news/1030402/>
- White, D., Goddard, L., & Wilbur, N. (2009). The effects of negative information transference in the celebrity endorsement relationship. *International Journal Of Retail & Distribution Management*, 37(4), 322-335. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/09590550910948556>
- Zipporah, M., & Mberia, H. (2014). The effects of celebrity endorsement in advertisements. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences*. DOI:10.6007/IJAREMS/v3-i5/1250